

Topological studies on benzodiazepine receptor binding

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Manuscript received 30 December 1998, revised 8 October 1999, accepted 11 November 1999

Molecular negentropy (N) and first order valence connectivity ${}^1\chi^v$ indices have been used for modeling nonbenzodiazepine series of benzodiazepine receptor ligands. The study reveals that these topological indices (N , ${}^1\chi^v$) work well only by coupling them with some molecular descriptors and by the introduction of indicator parameters. Regression analyses have indicated that excellent results are obtained when N , ${}^1\chi^v$, πR_1 , πR_3 , and RX_3 are used as correlating parameters.

Benzodiazepines and their receptors have opened a new era in the characterization of drugs acting on the central nervous system. The benzodiazepines have wide range of therapeutic applications¹. Many of the nonbenzodiazepines ligands have been subjected to quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR) by classical methodology using some of the structural parameters as the molecular descriptors. However, such QSAR studies do not give 1 : 1 correspondence because it was not possible to describe the molecular structure by a number like molecular properties and activities². It was only after the application of topological (graph theoretical) techniques to chemical compounds that it became possible to represent molecular structure by a number, thus giving 1 : 1 correspondence to structure-property-activity relationships.

According to chemical graph theory, a molecular structure can be transformed into its molecular graph by suppressing all the carbon-hydrogen bonds in the molecular structure³. In depicting a molecular graph, the atoms (vertices) are represented by a solid dot “•” or by small circle “o”, and the bonds (edges) as usual are represented by small lines “—”. By imposing certain conditions on atoms (vertices) or bonds (edges) or both (vertices and edges) a number can be obtained which represents structure numerically. Such a numerical representation of molecular structure is called topological index⁴. Several topological indices are reported in the literature^{3,4}. The one due to Wiener⁵ and the other due to Randić as modified by Kier have wide physicochemical and pharmacological applications⁶.

In the present investigation, we have used molecular negentropy (N) as well as first order valence connectivity (${}^1\chi^v$) indices introduced by Kier^{6,7} for topological modeling of benzodiazepine receptor binding of nonbenzodia-

zepine ligands. These ligands are related to thienylparalogoquinolines reported earlier⁸ and we have adopted these ligands and reported binding constants ($\log 1/K_d$) of these compounds in the present study. These binding constants were calculated using the relationship,

$$K = IC_{50}/(1 + C/K_d) \quad (1)$$

where, IC_{50} is the concentration of the test compound for 50% inhibition of the specific binding of [³H] diazepam, C the concentration of the radio-ligands used and K_d the apparent dissociation constant of the radioligand-receptor complex.

In addition to the aforementioned topological indices some structural parameters as well as indicator constants have also been used to account for the effect of a particular group at a given position. The coupling of these parameters with topological indices N and ${}^1\chi^v$ gave excellent results.

Calculation of molecular negentropy N : The method of calculation of molecular negentropy is the same as described by Kier⁷. First, the negentropy per atom i , is computed for the drug molecule using Shannon's formula⁹,

$$i = -K \sum_j P_j \log P_j \quad (2)$$

where K is a constant depending on the logarithmic base, j the set, and P_j the complete array of probabilities. Multiplying i with the total number of vertices (atoms), n gives the molecular negentropy (N),

$$N = i n \quad (3)$$

Here, \log_{10} is used for convenience. Use of \log_2 leads to negentropy in bites. Several properties of negentropy (N) are apparent: (i) The negentropy is maximal when all parts of the structure are unique, resulting in equal probabilities

for all parts, (ii) the negentropy is zero when all parts of the structure are equivalent and (iii) the numerical value of the negentropy decreases with greater multiplicity within each set or for a smaller number of sets.

First order valence connectivity index (${}^1\chi^v$): Kier⁶ modified the connectivity index proposed by Randic by considering the reciprocal of vertex degrees (topological valency of the atom). Accordingly, the first order valence connectivity index of Kier is given by the expression,

$${}^1\chi^v = \sum (\delta_i^v \delta_j^v)^{-1/2} \quad (4)$$

where δ_i^v and δ_j^v are the valence delta values for the atoms i and j respectively. Then, δ^v values were obtained by using equation (5),

$$\delta^v = \frac{Z^v - N_H}{Z - Z^v - 1} \quad (5)$$

where Z^v is the number of valence electron of atom i or j , N_H the number of hydrogen atoms attached to i or j , and Z the total number of electrons.

Results and Discussion

The nondiazepine series of ligands used in the present study along with their N , ${}^1\chi^v$ and other structural parameters are given in Table 1. Table 2 records the correlation matrix for the correlation of benzodiazepine receptor binding ($\log 1/K_d$) with the above mentioned topological indices and other structural invariants. The regression analyses and corresponding quality of correlation are presented in

Table 1. Nonbenzodiazepine series of ligands used, their topological indices (N and ${}^1\chi^v$) and other correlation parameters*

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	RX ₁	πR ₁	RX ₃	πR ₃	N	${}^1\chi^v$
1	Me	H	H	H	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	38.3822	5.9764
2	H	H	H	H	H	0	0.00	0	0.00	33.8976	5.7984
3	H	Me	H	H	H	0	0.00	0	0.00	38.1780	6.2151
4	H	H	Ac	H	H	0	0.00	0	-0.01	44.2201	6.6969
5	H	H	Carb	H	H	0	0.00	0	-0.32	40.2115	6.6909
6	Et	H	H	H	H	0	1.02	0	0.00	46.0180	6.7871
7	Cl	H	H	H	H	1	0.71	0	0.00	35.1017	5.9155
8	Me	H	Cl	H	H	1	0.56	1	0.71	39.3822	6.1880
9	Me	H	Br	H	H	0	0.56	1	0.86	39.3822	6.1880
10	Me	H	H	7-Cl	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	41.3359	5.5449
11	Me	H	H	8-Cl	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	41.3359	5.9449
12	Me	H	H	7-F	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	41.3359	5.9449
13	Me	H	H	8-F	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	41.3359	5.9449
14	Me	H	H	7-Me	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	45.7425	6.0060
15	Me	H	H	8-Me	H	0	0.56	0	0.00	45.7425	6.0060
16	Me	H	H	H	Me	0	0.56	0	0.00	43.7888	5.6121
17	Me	H	H	H	Et	0	0.56	0	0.00	50.1399	6.2283
18	n-Pr	H	H	H	H	0	1.55	0	0.00	48.1631	7.7099
19	i-Pr	H	H	H	H	0	1.53	0	0.00	48.3538	8.5233
20	n-But	H	H	H	H	0	2.13	0	0.00	47.7556	7.5799
21	i-But	H	H	H	H	0	2.28	0	0.00	48.6441	7.4764

* $\log 1/K_d$ = Benzodiazepine receptor binding; N = molecular negentropy; ${}^1\chi^v$ = First order valence connectivity index; πR_1 = steric interaction for R₁; πR_3 = steric interaction for R₃; indicator parameter for the presence of halogen at R₁ = RX₁, at R₂ = RX₂, at R₃ = RX₃.

Table 2. Correlation matrix for the correlation of benzodiazepine receptor binding with topological indices and structural parameters used*

	$\log 1/K_1$	N	${}^1\chi^v$	πR_1	πR_3	RX_1	RX_2	RX_3
$\log 1/K_1$	1.0000							
N	-0.2797	1.0000						
${}^1\chi^v$	0.1093	0.3580	1.0000					
πR_1	0.1888	0.6148	0.4335	1.0000				
πR_3	-0.1603	-0.1959	-0.1308	-0.0089	1.0000			
RX_1	0.1276	-0.3842	-0.1520	-0.0080	-0.0536	1.0000		
RX_2	-0.2218	-0.2460	-0.1343	-0.0894	0.9566	-0.0725	1.0000	
RX_3	0.3441	-0.1553	0.1577	-0.1337	-0.1163	-0.1084	-0.1573	1.0000

*Explanation of symbols same as in Table 1.

Table 3. Table 4 records the benzodiazepine receptor binding ($\log 1/K_1$) estimated from the excellent correlation. Monivariate as well as multivariate correlations were performed and the results are recorded in Table 3. The correlation matrix (Table 2) indicates that except for πR_3 and RX_3 , none of the parameters (Table 1) intercorrelate mutually. In addition, a poor correlation ($R = 0.6148$) was obtained between N and πR_1 . These results indicate that it is not possible to obtain any monivariate correlation of the receptor binding ($\log 1/K_1$) with any of the topological indices and other structural descriptors used.

Table 3. Regression parameters and quality of correlations of benzodiazepine receptor binding of some nonbenzodiazepine series of ligands*

- (1) $\log 1/K_1 = (0.0094)N - (0.03013)\pi R_1 - (1.6300)\pi R_3 + 9.0023$
Sd = 0.2032, $R = 0.9225$, $F = 24.756$
- (2) $\log 1/K_1 = -(0.0292){}^1\chi^v - (0.2267)\pi R_1 - (1.6591)\pi R_3 + 9.5363$
Sd = 0.2028, $R = 0.9228$, $F = 24.875$
- (3) $\log 1/K_1 = -(0.0337)N - (5.0667)\pi R_3 + (2.7123)RX_3 + 10.1486$
Sd = 0.22262, $R = 0.9063$, $F = 19.940$
- (4) $\log 1/K_1 = (0.0110)N - (0.0335){}^1\chi^v - (0.2833)\pi R_3 - (1.6396)\pi R_3 + 9.1438$
Sd = 0.2080, $R = 0.9252$, $F = 17.820$
- (5) $\log 1/K_1 = (0.0116)N - (0.0328){}^1\chi^v - (0.2846)\pi R_1 - (5.0667)\pi R_3 + (2.7199)RX_3 + 9.1129$
Sd = 0.1873, $R = 0.9450$, $F = 18.355$

*Sd = Standard error of estimation; R = Multiple correlation coefficient; F = F -ratio.

During the process of evaluating the best possible regression we observed that in the tri-parametric correlation, collinearity between the receptor binding ($\log 1/K_1$) is observed when N and ${}^1\chi^v$ are coupled with other structural descriptors (Table 3). The best correlations are obtained for the ter-variate correlation : (i) N , πR_1 and πR_3 , (ii) ${}^1\chi^v$, πR_1 and πR_3 , and (iii) N , πR_3 and RX_3 . The quality of correlation in all these three cases was found to be very simi-

Table 4. Estimated activity from regression equation (5)

Compd. no	Receptor binding activity		
	Obs.	Est.	Residue
1	9.49	9.21	0.28
2	9.14	9.22	-0.18
3	8.16	9.35	-1.19
4	6.86	6.84	0.00
5	7.75	7.75	0.00
6	9.39	9.12	0.27
7	9.14	9.12	0.02
8	8.33	8.33	0.00
9	7.57	7.57	0.00
10	9.11	9.11	0.00
11	9.20	9.23	-0.03
12	9.19	9.23	-0.04
13	9.43	9.24	0.19
14	9.02	9.28	-0.26
15	9.42	9.29	0.13
16	6.66	6.66	0.00
17	6.66	6.66	0.00
18	8.98	8.99	-0.01
19	9.02	8.96	0.06
20	8.73	8.81	-0.08
21	8.64	8.78	-0.14

lar. It is worth recording that the coupling of ${}^1\chi^v$ with πR_3 and RX_3 gave no significant correlation with the receptor binding ($\log 1/K_1$). Further attempts of obtaining better correlations indicated that the tetrivariate correlations were as good as the ter-variate correlations. In all the possible tetrivariate correlations the quality was found to be the same as indicated by their correlation coefficient of the order of 0.92. Finally, excellent multivariate correlation is obtained when both the topological indices N , ${}^1\chi^v$ were coupled together with πR_1 , πR_3 and RX_3 . In this case, the standard deviation was found to be the least and the correlation coefficient was found to be the highest (Table 3).

On the basis of the various regression parameters presented in Table 3, the aforementioned excellent correlation takes the following form,

$$\log 1/K_1 = (0.0116)N - (0.0328)^1\chi^v - (0.2846)\pi R_1 - (5.0667)\pi R_3 + (2.7199)RX_3 + 9.1129 \quad (6)$$

This correlation seems to be highly significant and accounts for about 90% of the variance in the binding receptor activity.

In addition to the topological indices (N , $^1\chi^v$), three other structural parameters (πR_1 , πR_3 and RX_3) are involved in this correlation. Out of these, πR_1 and πR_3 have negative coefficients. These negative coefficients indicate that the substituents at R_1 and R_3 positions are not conducive to the binding affinity. From these results we conclude that either no substituent or a substituent with a hydrophobic-lipophobic balance is most favorable at positions R_1 and R_3 . It was also observed that RX_3 has a positive coefficient indicating the positive role of substituents at R_3 in exhibiting the receptor binding activity.

In order to investigate the receptor binding potential of the compounds used we have finally estimated the receptor binding ($\log 1/K_1$) using equation (6). The estimated values are then compared with the observed (experimental) binding receptor activity. These data are presented in Table 4. A comparison of the estimated binding receptor ability with the observed ones shows that the parameters πR_1 , πR_3 and RX_3 are well qualified for the prediction of the receptor binding activity.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.K.A.) is thankful to AICTE, New

Delhi, for financial support. The authors acknowledge the computer facilities made available through this grant.

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